

TECHNOLOGIES OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE TO STUDENTS OF GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS ON THE BASE OF INDIVIDUAL APPROACH

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Abstract. *The individual directions of educational activities used in the planning of students' activities require the development of educational content and methods to strengthen educational and methodological support, expand and deepen students' knowledge and skills.*

The article describes the technologies of teaching English to students of general education schools based on an individual approach, the concept of "individual orientation", requirements for educational content.

Keywords: *content, method, direction, goal, activity, result, direction, competence, experience.*

Introduction

General education schools should create conditions for independent planning of students' educational activities, formation of flexible individual educational directions that allow mastering of academic subjects at the basic and advanced level. In E. V. Ospennikova's [5] research on solving the problem of organizing the individual activities of students in the class team, the task of organizing education based on an individual approach is solved based on the classification of students according to the levels of educational needs, which is used by the teacher in planning the activities of students enables the development of educational and methodological support for the implementation of individual directions. However, the author did not provide an opportunity to quickly change the direction based on the results of the interim control of the educational content, methods and further rapid correction for expanding and deepening the knowledge and skills of students.

Based on the ability to quickly change the content and methods of education, we define the concept of "individual orientation" as a set of consistently obtained results of educational activities aimed at achieving personally important educational goals. By the formation of an individual direction of learning a subject, we mean the design of educational activities (preliminary planning of activities for the academic period), the implementation of educational activities (consistent collection and collection of educational results), the management of educational activities based on the determination of the conformity/incompatibility of the student's educational results with personally important goals (we understand changing the situation in the initial activity plan).

The research of many authors is devoted to the study of problems related to the use of an individual approach in secondary schools. Analysis of the scientific and methodological literature of domestic and foreign authors (V.P. Bepalko, M.V. Klarin, V.M. Monakhov, I.E. Unt, I.S. Yakimanskaya, etc.) on the problem of individualization of the educational process shows that , in science and practice, there are the following approaches to scientific research and development in

this field: an approach that includes the individual development of a holistic system of the educational process directed by the teacher in order to achieve high results in education (child development); an approach focused on the technologicalization of the educational process (use of distance education technologies) with the student's participation in extracurricular activities.

Based on an individual approach, we consider it appropriate to implement the principles of cooperation methodology, such as ease of tasks for each student, creation of a situation for success in education, use of basic schemes representing the graphic state of the studied subject, gradual transition to complete independence in mastering the subject.

Many modern representatives of the science and practice of pedagogy are conducting research in the direction of integrating the humanistic approach aimed at increasing the share of independent activity of students and the technological approach to education aimed at achieving the repetition of educational results. As an example, G.K.Selevko's self-developing educational technology, V.P.Bespalko's concept of personalized education, V.M.Monakhov's pedagogical technologies can be cited, which can be used to teach English to students of general education schools based on a partially individual approach.

Method

The individual approach is also reflected in the modern concept of language teaching, which plays an important role in the formation of the personality of a student of any educational institution. Studying the importance of the process of teaching foreign languages should be recognized not only in the formation of private speech competences, but also in influencing the personality of learners, as a result of which he becomes a self-developing organism, acquires meaningful and reflexive behavioral experience, and the ability of creative cognitive activity.

Addressing the topic of the human factor in language has contributed to a paradigm shift in linguistics. There is a transition from the study of personal linguistics to the study of anthropological linguistics, in the center of which is the individual with his mental characteristics, forms of social existence and cultural activity. The ideas of anthropocentrism, which appeared at the end of the twentieth century, changed the linguo-philosophical views about the nature of language and, accordingly, the direction of the content of the modern paradigm of language teaching, because any model of language teaching is based on the "language image" that exists in each specific period of linguistic development.

Representatives of various disciplines together managed to determine the role of language in knowledge and philosophical perception of the world, its importance as a means of expressing and constructing thoughts, in the formation and development of a person, in his culture. In this regard, it is worth noting that the versatility of philosophy, logic and linguistics unites them in the desire to reveal the mechanism of human knowledge, the relationship between thinking, language and reality - the desire to determine the "meaning of an idea", "knowledge of understanding".

At a certain stage of the development of science and society, it is necessary to focus on the following main methodical categories that determine the ideology of this educational subject: educational goals, educational content, educational principles.

The goal of teaching foreign languages can be legally considered a socio-methodical category, because it is determined not only by a certain concept of general education, but also by the social order of the state regarding language teaching to its citizens. At the same time, it can be defined as a multifaceted category, it should be noted that in the methodology of teaching foreign

languages, practical, general education, educational and developmental goals of education are traditionally distinguished [2].

At the same time, in the foreign and domestic literature of recent years, the question of the global/strategic goal of education, which is a reflection of the social order of society in the field of language learning, is raised. According to some scientists, this is the formation of bilingual personality traits in learners [10], according to other scientists, it is a characteristic of a person who knows the language [4], which allows a person to participate in intercultural communication with representatives of other societies.

The second main category of methodology is the content of foreign language education, which is closely related to the educational goals and depends on it.

Under the influence of this interpretation, the following are currently included in the educational content:

- spheres of communication - teaching socio-communicative language, which differs according to the forms of existence and is related to some types of words of a certain society;
- communication situations that include the unity of speech and non-speech situations that are necessary and sufficient to perform speech activity;
- topics of communication representing the topic of presentation and research and responding to the information nature of the areas of communication;
- texts that affect as a result of oral or written speech activity carried out in a certain area of communication;
- knowledge of the language - knowledge of the language system and rules of use in theoretical and practical activities.
- speech operations characterized by automaticity, compliance with language standards, normal pace (speed of execution, stability), skills. Language skills are automatic components of conscious speech activity in oral and written form [10];
- solving communication skills based on the developed skills of a person, showing the correct choice of speech style, using the most effective speech and non-speech tools for the given conditions, skills that include subordinating the form of speech to communication tasks [11];
- the experience of emotional reaction to objects of reality acquired during the educational process [1];
- competences that are manifested as a result of education and indicate readiness to perform any activity based on knowledge, skills, competences and work experience acquired in the educational process. The modern interpretation of communicative competence includes the following types of competence: linguistic, socio-linguistic (language), discursive, strategic, social, socio-cultural, professional [10].

This is the content of the main categories of the foreign language teaching process and the basic characteristics of "English" as a subject of study in the language teaching system. Its modern significance in human development is incomparable as it is characterized by deep integration processes, unprecedented rise of international cooperation. Knowledge of languages and, first of all, knowledge of international communication languages is an important indicator of modern education. Forming the consciousness of the individual, his capacity for social mobility, it serves as an important tool for a successful human life in a multicultural and multilingual society, provides access to diverse world politics and culture, and contributes to mutual understanding between peoples who speak different languages and cultures.

Results and discussion

The technologies of teaching English to students of general education schools on the basis of an individual approach are represented by four traditional competencies: linguistic, socio-cultural, pragmatic and strategic, their interpretation is given above. The formation of these competencies takes place in the first years of studying the English language course in general schools and meets the goals of learning to use language in social communication situations, which is a very broad concept.

From the perspective of communicative speech practice, students should be involved in preparing and performing abstracts, especially reading scientific and technical sources on the Internet, analyzing and understanding scientific articles, conference proceedings, inventions and patents. For this, it is useful to have small group discussions on the following topics:

- the work is not done until it is communicated;
- elements of every communication;
- methods of communication;
- message: what, how, when, why, who;
- graphics in communication;
- readability of texts;
- writing a paper: length, contents, title, abstract, nomenclature, body of paper, headings, mathematics, figures, tables, acknowledgments, writing the text of the article: volume, content, title, abstract, used terms and abbreviations, main text, section titles, mathematical expressions, figures, tables, acknowledgments.

The practice of conducting classes on the principle of "senior seminar" will be interesting. In the introductory lesson, the teacher talks about the scientific side of the topic, gives examples of written and oral scientific information. Students are then asked to select several current research topics and tasked with reading, extracting, and recording relevant and relevant information. Then they collect information from English-language sources and organize it according to the principle: research object, research subject, research methods, expected results, proven results, environmental impact, conclusions.

A presentation in Power Point format is prepared for oral communication. Such a "senior seminar" is prepared before the graduation project ("graduation project"), its task is to develop all kinds of reading skills, reproductive writing skills and communication skills in working with information. The topic of the messages may correspond to the topics of the thesis, but it is not mandatory.

Individual teaching of foreign language subjects with other subjects, due to the superiority of subjects, communicative orientation and professional orientation, objectively helps students to change their motives for knowledge into professional motives, and as a result, to form a skilled person.

1. The principle of psychological and pedagogical support of the student's personal involvement in educational activities. The implementation of the principle is ensured by meeting the needs of the student in the course of English language learning activities and their subsequent continuation.

2. The principle of consistent modeling of the overall content, forms and conditions of professional activity of specialists in the educational activities of students. The content and form

of education changes during the transition from education to quasi-professional to professional educational activities at different stages.

3. The principle of problematic in the process of educational content and its placement in the educational process. Building the material according to the principle of problem solving is a necessary condition of individual education, it ensures the constant interest of students and gives personal content to the acquired knowledge.

4. The principle of conformity of forms of organization of students' educational activities with the purpose and content of education. At the initial stage, individual education is carried out in the form of traditional lectures and practical exercises. The format of the lessons is then changed to include discussions, brainstorming, small projects, discussion of problem situations, development of oral communication skills, lecture, discussion of engineering/scientific writing technology.

5. The principle of the leading importance of the joint activity of the subjects of the educational process (teacher and students, students among themselves), interpersonal joint action and dialogic communication. Individual education can be imagined as a dialogue about modern engineering activities. The interests and wishes of the students are taken into account when determining the content of the lessons. Speaking skills related to speaking are practiced in small groups.

6. The principle of pedagogically based harmony of new and traditional pedagogical technologies. At the initial stage of individual education, traditional technologies are used. As students acquire reading skills, elements of design and computer-based instruction are introduced as needed.

7. The principle of openness is the use of any pedagogical technologies proposed within the framework of other theories and approaches to achieve the specific goals of education and upbringing in the context-type educational process. Individual education is focused on the result - students' acquisition of foreign language communicative competence in the selection of teaching forms, methods and content, pedagogical technologies developed in the theory of educational development, the content of the educational process, as well as the problem-based approach to the formation of ideas about the gradual formation of mental actions.

8. The principle of unity of education and upbringing of a specialist. During the educational process, educational effectiveness is ensured due to the modeling of various aspects of professional engineering activities.

As it can be seen from the conducted analysis, individual education corresponds to the principles of contextual education, which confirms the possibilities of formation of professional motives of students.

Summary

On the basis of an individual approach, the technologies of teaching English to students of general education schools are also implemented with role-playing and business games.

Role-playing games are understood as a form of simulation modeling, that is, a specific model of mutual cooperation (cooperative or conflicting) of subjects in the environment of simulation of future professional activity conditions, during its implementation, certain skills of game participants are formed/improved. The term role-playing game appears as a general concept that means all the differences in the game, in which the participants of the game are divided into roles, and means improvisation to the existing situation, such as the game method.

Role playing is used as a method of socio-psychological training to improve communication skills. It helps to overcome language and communication barriers, including socio-perceptual type. As a result of its application, not only the ability to cooperate and the need to do it will be improved, but also their desire to make the cooperative relationship effective and productive will be formed. As a result, anxiety, tension, competitiveness, factors that negatively affect the mental health of the individual and the group are reduced.

Thus, in general, the analysis of methods, methodical systems, approaches, concepts, including the technologies of teaching English to students of general education schools on the basis of an individual approach, was carried out in the last decade, and the important innovations carried out by scientists at the present time are related to the practice of teaching foreign languages by English teachers. introduced, respects the achievements in this field of education, allows to draw a conclusion about the great research work.

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